

THE BEHAVIOUR OF ELECTROLYTES IN MIXED SOLUTIONS. PART I.
VISCOSITY OF KCl IN DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES AT 35°

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The viscosity of potassium chloride solution in dioxan-water mixtures at 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50% by weight of dioxan has been studied. Data obtained fit in excellently with a modified form of the Jones-Dole equation: $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^2$. 'B' has been found to depend upon the composition of the solvent. It is suggested that the composition of the sphere of solvation is responsible for the magnitude of 'B'.

The aim of the present investigation has been to test the applicability of the Jones-Dole equation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950) and in case of its non-applicability, to suggest a modified equation which would fit in with the experimental data. A satisfactory explanation has been advanced on theoretical grounds for 'A' by Falkenhagen and Vernon (*Phil. Mag.*, 1932, 14, 537), but no such explanation has yet been offered for the constant 'B'. It is also the aim of the present study to explore the nature of 'B' by the use of mixed solvents. We have therefore studied the relative viscosity of solutions of potassium chloride in varying compositions of dioxan-water mixtures.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Potassium chloride and dioxan used were of E. Merck's "extrapure" quality. Potassium chloride was recrystallised from triple distilled conductivity water, dried at 180° for 24 hours and stored in vacuum. Dioxan was left in contact with sodium wire for a week, then distilled and the middle fraction was used. At all stages of the experiment, rigorous precautions were taken to guard against evaporation of the non-aqueous component. To avoid evaporation, two limbs of the viscometer were attached to two flasks containing the same liquid. This arrangement was left undisturbed even when taking readings. All other experimental procedures were the same as recorded by Das (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 333) except that a further check of the vertical setting of the viscometer was done with a spirit level. The conductance readings were accurate to 2 in 1000. The working temperature was 35° ± 0.005°.

TABLE I

Solvent comp = 50%.			Solv. comp = 40%.		Solv. comp. = 30%.		Solv comp. = 20%.		Solv comp. = 10%.	
η/η_0 .			η/η_0 .		η/η_0 .		η/η_0 .		η/η_0 .	
*Conc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
0.1000	1.0151	1.0155	1.0119	1.0125	1.0080	1.0084	1.0061	1.0062	1.0041	1.0040
0.0750	1.0120	1.0120	1.0093	1.0096	1.0071	1.0067	1.0049	1.0049	1.0032	1.0032
0.0500	1.0088	1.0084	1.0066	1.0068	1.0048	1.0049	1.0037	1.0036	1.0025	1.0024
0.0250	1.0045	1.0046	1.0039	1.0037	1.0029	1.0029	1.0021	1.0021	1.0016	1.0015
0.0100	1.0020	1.0022	1.0017	1.0018	1.0017	1.0014	1.0011	1.0013	1.0008	1.0008
0.0075	1.0011	1.0017	1.0014	1.0014	1.0014	1.0012	1.0010	1.0009	1.0007	1.0007
0.0050	1.0009	1.0013	1.0009	1.0011	1.0009	1.0009	1.0006	1.0007	1.0004	1.0006
0.0025	1.0006	1.0008	1.0006	1.0006	1.0006	1.0006	1.0003	1.0005	1.0002	1.0004
0.0010	1.0004	1.0004	1.0004	1.0004	1.0003	1.0003	1.0003	1.0001	1.0001	1.0002

†No. of grams of dioxan per 100 grams of the mixture.

*Conc. in g. moles/litre.

TABLE II

Conc.	Solv. comp. = 50%.		Solv. comp. = 40%.		Solv. comp. = 30%.		Solv. comp. = 20%.		Solv. comp. = 10%.	
	$\Lambda_{\text{ohm}^{-1}}$	$\Lambda_{\infty\text{ohm}^{-1}}$								
0.0100	60.1		75.7		99.4		111.4		139.4	
0.0075	60.7		76.8		100.8		112.5		139.8	
0.0050	61.7	66.0	78.0	83.25	101.6	108.5	113.8	120.0	140.3	142.2
0.0025	62.7		79.4		104.2		115.2		140.9	
0.0010	63.9		81.0		105.6		117.1		141.4	

TABLE III

Composition of the solvent.	$A \times 10^3$.	x .	$B \times 10^3$.
50%	9.22	1.00	12.6
40	7.82	1.00	10.0
30	6.93	0.92	5.25
20	6.84	0.99	3.98
10	6.64	1.02	2.00

DISCUSSION

The change in viscosity with concentration for aqueous solutions of electrolytes is represented satisfactorily by the Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and the solvent, C is the concentration, and A and B are constants. The value of 'A' can be calculated by using Falkenhagen and Vernons' equation (*loc. cit.*) with a knowledge of the mobility of the constituent ions, the viscosity and the dielectric constant of the medium. In Table II the equivalent conductivities of potassium chloride solution at different composition of dioxan-water mixtures are shown and from these data, the equivalent conductivities at infinite dilution were obtained by plotting the equivalent conductivity against the square root of concentration and extrapolating the line to zero concentration. With the assumption that K^+ and Cl^- ions contribute equally towards the conductance at infinite dilution and using the data of Åkerlöf and Short (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1241) for dielectric constant of the medium, 'A' was calculated. The usual procedure to test the validity of the Jones-Dole equation is first to see if a straight

line is obtained by the plot of $\eta/(\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ against $\sqrt{C}$ and from the intercept of the straight line the value of 'A' can be obtained graphically. The satisfactory agreement between the calculated value of 'A' and that obtained by the graphical method is a further test of the Jones-Dole equation. The experimental data recorded in Table I do not satisfy the first test for the applicability of the Jones-Dole equation. The results are found to be satisfactorily represented if a slightly modified form of the Jones-Dole equation is employed:

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^x \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

In this equation 'A' remains unaltered in both form and implication. When x is one, the modified equation reduces to the original Jones-Dole equation. It is evident from equation (2) that the plot of $\log \{\eta/\eta_0 - (1 + A\sqrt{C})\}$ against $\log C$ would give a straight line, and from the slope and the intercept, the values of x and 'B' could be calculated. The values of x , 'A' and 'B' for potassium chloride solution at different composition of dioxan-water mixtures are recorded in Table III.

To explain the nature of 'B', Cox and Wolfenden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, 145A, 475) have attributed specific additive character to 'B', depending on the constituent ions. Since a single electrolyte, namely potassium chloride, has been used, the additive property attributed to 'B' is of not much avail. Asmus (*Z. Naturforsch.*, 1949 4a, 589) on the other hand suggests 'B' to be dependent on the lyotropic number and the entropy of hydrogen of the ionic species present in the medium. For aqueous solutions, Asmus' idea although relates the solvent to 'B', yet no direct proof has been advanced. A direct proof can be expected if 'B' changes with the change of composition of the solvent. This is only possible when a mixed solvent is used. The data recorded in Table III show that with the increase of the dioxan content in the solvent, the value of 'B' also increases, thus furnishing the proof that the magnitude of 'B' is dependent on the composition of the solvent.

We suggest that the sphere of solvation of the ions is responsible for the value of 'B'. In a single solvent, the solvation sphere is composed of only one type of molecule, and therefore it is the lyotropic number, as suggested by Asmus (*loc. cit.*), which determines the value of 'B'. In case of a mixed solvent, the solvation sphere will be composed of the molecules of the constituent components. Obviously, it is the nature and the number of molecules constituting the solvation sphere which would be responsible for 'B'. Hence, for a mixed solvent containing two types of molecules, it is to be expected that the value of 'B' would change with the change in composition of the mixture. The data recorded above fulfill this expectation.